

Determination of establish point of sugar beet plant for use in automatic thinning machine

Abdolabbas Jafari^{1,2}, Amir Mohammadi¹

¹ Biosystems Engineering Dept., Shiraz University

² Lincoln Agritech Ltd., Lincoln, New Zealand

Abstract

Even in the most modern machines, thinning of the crops is done by considering the distance between the crops while they are not accurate enough to detect the exact location of the plant. Detecting the establish point of the plant is one of the main requisites for autonomous thinning and weeding machines. In this study, it was tried to determine the establish point of the sugar beet plant through different approaches. The performance of the algorithms was then verified based on the difference in estimation of a establish point with the actual location of the point. Results showed that

All three algorithms were able to determine the establish point at early growth stage with an acceptable tolerance respect to the actual location. Evaluation of the methods for determining the establish point of the sugar beet showed that when sugar beet plants were small and in a range of 3 to 5 leaves, the Hough approach was preferable while in later growth stages up to 8 leaves, centroid and regression approach could produce a better result while variation of the plant shape and residual noises in the image has the lowest influence on the performance of the Hough method.

Keywords: Precision agriculture, machine vision, image processing, weeding robot

Introduction

One of the main problems of the existing thinner machines is that they thin the crops randomly and unintelligently. Recently sugar beet seed is planted by row crop machines with seed distances of 8 to 10 centimetres and then when the crop grew up to 3 or 4 leaves the crop distances would be dilated to 20 centimetres. Therefore in this situation, it is highly important to precisely determine the establish point of the plant needed to be retained. Sugar beet plants might be mistakenly cut due to inaccurate determination of their establish points which in turn would reduce the overall yield of the field.

The most common and promising method for locating the main stem of the plant is the centroid of the image (Jia & Krutz, 1992). This method is based on detection of individual leaves while each leaf location is described by the center of mass and petiole location. An average error up to 3 mm has been reported for stem location through this method (Midtiby et al. 2012).

Manoeuvring the agricultural robots in the fields is one of the applications of Hough transform for determination of the orientation of row crop plants. Hough transform has been widely used for detecting the crop rows and guidance of autonomous vehicles in the fields (Bakker et al. 2008; Ronghua and Lijun 2011; Montalvo et al. 2012; Jiang et al 2016).

Due to the importance of localisation of the main stem of the crop in weeding and thinning operations, an accurate detection algorithm is needed. Therefore the objective of this study was to develop the algorithms to determine the establish point of the crop plant based on the features extractable from images. This point can be used in precise thinning and weeding algorithms to save the crop plants from the unwanted cut.

Material and methods

Images needed for these experiments were collected from sugar beet plants in the field at two stages including 3 to 4 leaves and more than 8 leaves to determine the effectiveness of the algorithms at different growth stages.

An algorithm was designed to determine a point of sugar beet plant as the establish point of the plant. Three approaches were developed and evaluated in the algorithms including 'centroid', 'Hough transform' and 'regression'. The algorithms written by these three techniques were employed at two growth stages of 3 to 4 leaves and beyond 8 leaves using 30 images at each growth stage.

The first common step for all three methods was segmentation of the plants from the surrounding soil which was done by excessive green method as shown in figure 1.

Figure 1. Sugar beet as the main crop (left) and green plants segmented from the soil (right)

Other pre-processing operations exerted on the images included morphological operations for removing the small weeds around the main crop and filling the cavities inside the sugar beet leaves.

For the first method, the centroid of the area was considered as the establish point of the plant. In this method, non-weighted centroid was calculated using the area captured by each labelled sugar beet plants in the binary images.

In the second method, veins of the leaves were segmented from the main RGB images. To provide an image merely composed of sugar beet plants, the binary images created after morphological operations in the last stage, was integrated with the initial colour image using a logical AND operation between these two images. Since the images were taken at normal outdoor conditions, it was not possible to segment the veins from the rest of the leave by using a constant threshold.

On the other hand, the intensity and colour of the leaves, as well as the rest of the leave were extensively changing in different location of the images and the field while the veins were still recognizable in the leaves. This was referred as the local difference of the veins with other parts of the leaves. Therefore a dynamic thresholding was used to segment the veins based on their difference with surrounding neighbours. Since the surrounding pixels can be of any size, several block sizes were considered and tested to verify the best performance.

The procedure was tested for each of the RGB colour channels separately as well as HSV colour space channels. The best segmentation result can be seen in figure 2.

Figure 2. Detection of the veins on the leaves

As it can be seen in Figure 2, there are still other parts of the leaves in the image wrongly classified in the vein class. To discriminate the veins from the wrongly detected parts other features of the veins should be considered. Since the veins have a significantly different aspect ratio due to their length, they could be separated from the other objects. Therefore the aspect ratio of any shape in the binary image was used as criteria for this segmentation.

The result gained from this stage was used in the second method of determining the establish point of the plant which used Hough transform for detecting the veins lines. This method relied on the fact that the leaves vein reach together from the establish point. Therefore it was tried to find the point of convergence of these lines. It was needed at first to determine the orientation of these lines. To do this, Hough transform was used after when the veins were segmented from the images. But it is obvious that all the lines extracted from this procedure would not necessarily converge in a single point. Therefore in the next step, a most reasonable point of convergence of the lines was developed and used in this algorithm to determine the establish point of the plant.

The third approach was based on the regression. This method also used the results gained from colour segmentation of the images to detect the veins. After that, regression modelling of the veins were used to reconstruct a line from the veins. Similar to Hough transform approach, these lines were used to show the orientation of the veins. Regression was also used in the next step to determine the most promising point of convergence of the lines as the establish point of the plant.

Results

Through investigating several channels in RGB and HSV colour components and different block sizes, the best result was gained when the colour component R and a block size of 25 pixels were used. The best segmentation rate gained at this stage was 80% for the aforementioned situations.

The average deviation of each recognised point from the real establish point determined by the inspector was considered as the accuracies of the methods in determining the establish point of the plant.

In the centroid approach, the average deviation from the establish point was 1.2 cm with a standard deviation of 0.8 cm. when the plants were at more than eight leaves stages, these average difference were 1.1 cm with a standard deviation of 1. The reason that the deviation has been diminished as plant has grown is that the area captured by the plant has increased and the plant has got a more symmetrical shape comparing to early growth stages with 3 or 4 leaves. Therefore the centroid of the area captured by the plant has more coincidence with the actual establish point of the plant.

Despite the popularity of this method which is because of its lower calculations and consequently higher speed of determination, an important issue with this method is the occlusion and overlapping of the leaves with adjacent plants which makes the centroid of the plants completely different from the actual establish point. Therefore this method cannot be used for the late growth stages of sugar beets.

In Hough transform approach, the best result was gained when plants were at early growth stages when the orientation of the leaves easily transmit the establish point. The results showed that the average error of the method was 1.1 cm with a standard deviation of 1 cm when plants are at 3 to 4 leaves stages. But when the plant \the plants are grown up (more than 8 leaves stage) the orientation of the leaves does not accurately show the point of establishment. The reason can be referred to the fact t that the leaves in this stages could be curled and correspondingly the veins are curved and their orientation is not accurately pointing toward the establish point of the plant. The average difference between the actual and determined establish point of the plant in eight leaves stage was 1.7 and 1.5 cm respectively.

In the third approach based on the regression, the result was almost the same at 3 to 4 leaves stage while it had significant difference with the other two methods at more than 8 leaves stages. The average deviations of the regression method from the actual establish point was 2.4 cm which is more than the last two methods. The reason for this increase in the error can be referred to the fact that noises appeared from inaccurate segmentation of the vein can change the direction of the estimated lines more than the way they affect the Hough transform method.

A comparison between the errors of estimation in the three methods at two different growth stages of 3 to 4 leaves and 8 leaves has been shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. The accuracy of the methods in determination of establish point of plant

Conclusion

Determination of the establish point of plants was tried in this study for further use in thinning and weeding machines. Comparison between three different approaches i.e. Centroid, Hough, and regression showed that all three algorithms were able to determine the establish point at early growth stage with an acceptable tolerance respect to the actual location. At the second growth stage, in the 'centroid' approach, mean tolerance diminished to 0.05 cm whose reason was the higher symmetry appears at higher growth stages. For the other two approaches, the distance between the recognized establish point and actual establish point was increased when the plants were grown up. In Hough approach, the reason for increased inaccuracy was the curling of the leaves which has deviated the orienting line toward a wrong point while in regression approach, in addition to the curling of the leaves, the effect of the noises and inaccurate vein segmentation also influenced the imperfect determination of the vein line orientation.

Evaluation of the methods for determining the establish point of the sugar beet showed that when sugar beet plants were small and in a range of 3 to 5 leaves, the Hough approach was preferable while in later growth stages up to 8 leaves, centroid and regression approach could produce a better result. On the other hand, variation of the plant shape and residual noises in the image has the lowest influence on the performance of the Hough method.

References

Bakker T, Wouters H, Asselt K, Bontsema J, Tang L, Müller J, Straten G 2008. A vision based row detection system for sugar beet. *Computers and Electronics in Agriculture* 60(1): 87–95.

Jia J, Krutz G 1992. Location of the maize plant with machine vision. *Journal of agricultural engineering research* 52: 169–181.

Jiang G, Wang X, Wang Z, Liu H 2016. Wheat rows detection at the early growth stage based on Hough transform and vanishing point. *Computers and Electronics in Agriculture* 123: 211–223.

Midtby HS, Giselsson TM, Jørgensen RN 2012. Estimating the plant stem emerging points (PSEPs) of sugar beets at early growth stages. *Biosystems Engineering* 111(1): 83–90.

Montalvo M, Pajares G, Guerrerob JM, Romeo J, Guijarro M, Ribeiro A, Ruza JJ, Cruz JM 2012. Automatic detection of crop rows in maize fields with high weeds pressure. *Expert Systems with Applications* 39(15): 11889–11897.

Ronghua J, Lijun Q 2011. Crop-row detection algorithm based on random Hough transformation. *Mathematical and Computer Modelling* 54(3-4): 1016–1020.